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Comparative Study to Assess the Knowledge and Attitude of Rural and Urban Men (30-50 Years) Regarding Vasectomy

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Abstract:

Vasectomy is the most effective permanent family planning method but Acceptance of male permanent family planning method is very poor when compare to female methods. Non-experimental Quantitative research approach with Descriptive-comparative research design was adopted. The aim of the study is to assess the knowledge and attitude of rural and urban men (30-50 years) regarding vasectomy in Erode District. A Non-probability purposive sampling technique was used for selecting 60 married men (30 rural and 30 urban) who met the designated criteria during the period of data Collection. The data was collected by using tool, which consist of three sections: Section 1: Demographic Data, Section 2: Structured Knowledge questionnaire, Section 3: Attitude scale. The finding of the study reveals that the mean score and standard deviation of knowledge score in urban men was 15.26 ± 2.273 whereas the rural men mean score and standard deviation of knowledge was 10.4 ± 2.472 . The calculated 't' value 7.937, shows that the p value (< 0.0001) was statistically significant when

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compare to the rural men knowledge level regarding vasectomy. Similarly regarding attitude the mean score and standard deviation of urban men was 33.2 ± 6.504 whereas the rural men mean score and standard deviation of knowledge was 26.7 ± 7.758 . The calculated 't' value 3.481, shows that the p value (< 0.010) was statistically significant when compare to the rural men attitude regarding vasectomy. Conclusion: Lack of initiation and motivation, misconception about vasectomy and its health consequences contributes to the poor involvement and sharing responsibility of men. Therefore they need awareness through various programs like self instruction modules, mass health education, etc.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Urban, Rural, Population and Vasectomy.

Introduction:

Demography, as understood today, is the scientific study of human population⁽¹⁾. The population on the planet earth is increasing very fast because of decline death rate and high birth rate⁽²⁾. In 2009, world population stood at 6.8 billion, up about 83 million from 2008. The world total is likely to reach 7 billion in the latter half of 2011, with the bulk of growth in the world's poorest nations⁽³⁾.

High crude birth rate and fertility rate indicate rapid increase in population, which calls for birth control measures. If the birth control measures are effective, there should be a fall in birth rate and fertility rate⁽⁴⁾. Family planning is not synonymous with birth control but as per WHO family planning help the individual and couples to attain the certain objectives⁽⁵⁾. India was the first country to start family planning programme in 1951⁽⁶⁾.

Male participation has always been lower in health schemes and main reason is the mind set of both male and female. Vasectomy, male condom, withdrawal and abstinence are the common contraceptives available for men^(1,5). The most popular method of contraception is sterilization; about 98 percent are women with men contributing very little.

Vasectomy or permanent male surgical sterilization involves ligation, removal or destruction of small portion of vas deferens to prevent sperm from reaching to the urethra^(7, 8, 9) and ⁽¹⁰⁾. Vasectomy has more positive outlook

compare to tubal ligation of female sterilisation. Vasectomy is simple, safe, less expensive than female sterilisation but it is under used worldwide^(11, 12, 13). Barrier to vasectomy acceptance is include the fear of men about one or more of their children would died, then no longer have the ability to reproduce, and also fear about unable to remarry after their wives death⁽¹⁴⁾, fear of impotence, risky procedure, unable to do heavy work etc⁽¹¹⁾.

It is essential for all stakeholders to give urgent attention to behaviour change plan that can be put in action to improve the effects of these negative attitudes and misbelieves. The health care professional should help to improve the acceptance of vasectomy by men and encourage both the couples, clear their misconception highlight the benefit of vasectomy than tubectomy in rural and urban people and reduce the government expenditure and improve the quality of life.

Statement of the problem:

“A comparative study to assess the knowledge and attitude of rural and urban men (30-50 years) regarding vasectomy in selected areas of Appakudal and Bhavani at Erode district”.

Objectives:

1. To assess the knowledge and attitude of rural and urban men regarding vasectomy.
2. To compare knowledge and attitude of rural and urban men regarding vasectomy.
3. To find out correlation between knowledge and attitude of rural and urban men regarding vasectomy.
4. To find out association between demographic variables with knowledge and attitude of urban and rural men regarding vasectomy.

Hypotheses:

H₁: There is a significant difference between knowledge and attitude of rural and urban men regarding vasectomy.

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H₂: There is a significant correlation between knowledge and attitude of urban men regarding vasectomy.

H₃: There is a significant association between knowledge and attitude of rural and urban men with their selected demographic variables such as age, religion, occupation, education, income per month, number of living children in the family regarding vasectomy.

Research Methodology:

Non-experimental Quantitative research approach with Descriptive-comparative research design was adopted. The study was conducted at rural (Appakudal) and urban (Bhavani) areas in Erode District. The population of the study was all married men 30-50 years, who are residing in Erode district. A Non-probability purposive sampling technique was used for selecting 60 married men who met the designated criteria during the period of data Collection. The data was collected by using tool, which consist of three sections:

Section 1: Demographic Data.

Section 2: Structured Knowledge questionnaires.

Questionnaires to assess the aspect wise knowledge of rural and urban men regarding vasectomy. It consists of 3 subsections (Total - 20).

Subsection 1: 10 General knowledge questions on family welfare.

Subsection 2: 5 Knowledge Questions on health services regarding vasectomy.

Subsection 3: 5 Advanced Knowledge question on no scalpel vasectomy.

Scoring:

Each correct answer carries 1 mark.

Knowledge → 76% - 100% - Adequate

51% - 75% - Moderately adequate

50% below - Inadequate

Section 3: Attitude scale used to assess the attitude of the subjects on regarding vasectomy.

3 point Likert’s scale on attitude contains 15 questions regarding vasectomy among men in rural and urban area. It should be responded as strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree.

Scoring: 7 positive and 8 negative questions

For positive response:

- Agree - 3
- Neutral - 2
- Disagree - 1

For Negative Response:

- Agree - 1
- Neutral - 2
- Disagree -3

Result:

The data was organized as per the objectives

The first objective of the study was to assess the knowledge and attitude of rural and urban men regarding vasectomy.

Fig. no. 1: Cylinder diagram shows percentage distribution of level knowledge among rural men and urban men regarding vasectomy.

Figure no. 1, shows the level of knowledge, in that 17(56.67%) urban men had of adequate knowledge, 13(43.3%) had moderate knowledge and none of them had inadequate knowledge whereas among the rural men 18(60%) and 12(40%) had inadequate and moderate knowledge respectively.

Fig. no. 2: Cone diagram shows percentage distribution of Level of attitude among rural men and urban men regarding vasectomy.

Figure no. 2 illustrate the level of attitude of urban men had 50% of better attitude, 33.3% of good attitude and 16.67% of poor attitude whereas the rural men had 50%, 33.3% and 16.6% of poor, good and better attitude respectively towards vasectomy.

The second objective of the study was to compare knowledge and attitude of rural and urban men regarding vasectomy.

Table - 1: Overall comparisons of rural & urban men knowledge and attitude score

	Rural men		Urban men		Independent <i>t</i> -test
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Knowledge	10.4	2.472	15.26	2.273	$t = 7.937$ $P = < 0.0001$ Extremely Significant
Attitude	26.7	7.758	33.2	6.504	$t = 3.481$ $P = 0.010$ Extremely significant

Table - 1, reveals the mean and standard deviation of knowledge score in urban men was 15.26 ± 2.273 whereas the rural men mean score and standard deviation of knowledge was 10.4 ± 2.472 . The calculated '*t*' value 7.937, shows that the *p* value (< 0.0001) was statistically significant when compare to the rural men knowledge level regarding vasectomy.

Similarly regarding attitude the mean score and standard deviation of urban men was 33.2 ± 6.504 whereas the rural men mean score and standard deviation of knowledge was 26.7 ± 7.758 . The calculated '*t*' value 3.481, shows that the *p* value (< 0.010) was statistically significant when compare to the rural men knowledge level regarding vasectomy. **Hence H_1 hypothesis is accepted.**

In parallel to the present study, A. Dibaba was conducted a descriptive study on Rural men and their attitude towards vasectomy as means of contraception in Ethiopia. A descriptive study on the attitude of rural men towards vasectomy as means of contraception was conducted in south western Ethiopia. A total of 200 men who came to a rural health centre either for treatment or to accompany a patient were included for interview. The mean age of the interviewees was 30.9 and the main occupation was farming (67.5%). The mean number of offspring born to the respondents was 3.5 with 70% of the respondents wanting more children. Fifty-five per cent had heard about contraception before and in this group 31% of the wives used or were using one of the common methods. None of the respondents was against the use of contraceptives and none of them had heard previously of

vasectomy as means of contraception. The acceptance of vasectomy as means of contraception was 79%. Twenty-one per cent opposed vasectomy because of the problem of possible loss of children due to death or divorce. The high acceptance rate of vasectomy indicates an unmet need for surgical contraception and the training of health personnel on the 'no scalpel vasectomy' technique. Making this service available, starting at health centre level, is recommended⁽¹⁶⁾.

In parallel to the present study, S. Ghazal-Aswad¹, D.E. Rizk, S.M. Al-Khoori, H. Shaheen, L. Thomas was conducted a study to determine the knowledge and practice of contraception among United Arab Emirates (UAE) women. Four hundred women (89%) gave consent to participate in the study. One hundred and sixty-six participants (41.5%) were using contraception. All used natural methods backed with other methods. There were significant associations between using contraception and each of age, high level of education and low family income ($p < 0.0001$ for the three variables). Religious beliefs and low expectation of success of birth control were the reasons given for non-use. Eighty-five percent of subjects did not accept sterilisation without medical indications, nor using contraception before the first pregnancy. Of the women, 42.5% believed that contraceptive methods should not be used after the age of 40, and 78% were unaware that they could be used for treatment of gynaecological diseases. Disturbed bleeding patterns occurred in 48.7% of users, and these were most bothered by the inability to pray (100%) and to have sexual intercourse (97.5%)⁽¹⁷⁾.

The third objective of the study was to correlate knowledge and attitude of rural and urban men regarding vasectomy.

Pearson correlation coefficient is denoted by " r "

" r " always lies between -1 to +1

0.0 - 0.2 Poor correlation

0.2 - 0.4 fair correlation

0.4 - 0.6 moderate correlation

0.6 - 0.8 good correlation

0.8 - 1.0 strong correlation

Table - 2: Correlation between knowledge and attitude of rural and urban men regarding vasectomy

Test	Correlation	Mean Score		Interpretation
	Between	Mean \pm SD	Karl Pearson correlation coefficient	
Rural men	Knowledge	10.4 \pm 2.472	$r = 0.3579$	Fair positive correlation
	Attitude	26.7 \pm 7.758	$p = 0.0521$	
Urban men	Knowledge	15.26 \pm 2.273	$r = 0.06390$	Moderate positive correlation
	Attitude	33.2 \pm 6.504	$p = 0.7373$	

Table - 2 reveals the correlation between knowledge and attitude of rural men ' r ' = 0.3579 which shows fair positive correlation, whereas in urban men there was moderate positive correlation ' r ' = 0.06390. Hence it indicates that there is moderately positive attitude among the rural and urban men when they have adequate knowledge regarding vasectomy and vice versa. **Hence the H₂ hypothesis was accepted.**

The fourth objective of the study was to association between demographic variables with knowledge and attitude of urban and rural men regarding vasectomy.

There is an association between No. of living children with the level of knowledge in rural men. **Hence the H₃ hypothesis was accepted.**

Conclusion:

From the findings of the present study, it was inferred that the level of knowledge and attitude regarding vasectomy among the rural men was inadequate compare to urban men. But both the rural and urban men need to improve their knowledge and attitude regarding advanced vasectomy technique. Lack of initiation and motivation, misconception about methods and its health consequences contributes to the poor involvement and sharing responsibility of men. Therefore

they need awareness through various programs like self instruction modules, mass health education, etc.

Implication:

Nursing research: The present study findings will help the future investigator to carry out more extensive research on larger population with samples in different areas of community to shape the truth.

Nursing practise: The finding help the nurse and student to create awareness among the men through the self instruction modules regarding vasectomy in order to reduce the burden of the women and to promote the welfare of the family.

Nursing administration: Student nurse as a nurse administrator can conduct various programs in the community in sequence to encourage the men to poses good attitude and gain adequate knowledge regarding vasectomy.

Nursing education: The Nurse educator can emphasize on health education of Vasectomy and its practice as a part of learning experience for the students. They can also arrange for the in-service education programme (seminars, workshops) for nurses regarding Vasectomy and its practice.

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